

The Determinants of Employee Commitment (The Study Conducted On Ethiopian Public University Academic Staff - Wolaita Sodo University)

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to find out the Determinant Factors influencing Staff Commitment in Wolaita Sodo University. Specifically to identify the influence of rewards, career development, training and development opportunities and the management style on employee commitment. The study uses causal research design. All public institutions would like to be more efficient, cost determinative, accountable and responsive to the needs of its customers. Public service and particular public universities play an indispensable role in the determinative delivery of skilled workforce needed for the functioning of a state economy. Public universities have an important role in Ethiopia's socio-economic development. The target population is all Academic staff in Wolaita Sodo University. A questionnaire is the main data collection instruments. The study employs both quantitative and qualitative analysis techniques. A regression model used to analyze the objectives. Training and development is the best predictor variable for the university. Therefore, the researchers recommend the concerned bodies of the university to give more focus on future research endeavors that investigate factors that enhance any short and long term training besides the improvements their attachments of managerial style administrating and reward in realities. This research further implies there were strong correlations among the independent variables, future studies may work on modeling techniques to understand the influence each variable has on each other in detail.

Key Words: *Carrier development, commitment, Rewards, management styles, multi-regression*

1. Introduction

Employee commitment is a crucial 'work attitude' (Morris et al, 1993:22). It has been defined in several similar ways to emphasize its behavioral and psychological moorings. For instance: "... a stabilizing force that acts to maintain behavioral direction when expectancy/equity conditions are not met and do not function" (Locke, 1976: 1298)" and; "a psychological state that binds the individual to the organization" (Allen & Meyer, 1990:4). No organization in today's competitive world can perform at peak levels unless each employee is committed to the organization's objectives and works as an effective team member. It is no longer good enough to have employees who come to work faithfully every day and do their jobs independently. Employees now have to think like entrepreneurs while working in teams, and have to prove their worth. However, they also want to be part of a successful organization which provides a good income and the opportunity for development and secure employment. In the past, organizations secured the loyalty of their employees by guaranteeing job security. However, many organizations have responded to competitive pressures by downsizing, restructuring, and transformation and thus created a less secure organizational climate. A growing number of employees, therefore, feel that they are victims of broken promises. One of the challenges facing modern organizations involves maintaining employee commitment in the current business environment. This organization can achieve by developing a new "work contract". In today's workplace, employees face more ambiguity in their daily activities and decreased job security (Bergmann, Lester, De Meuse & Grahn, 2000).

With no assurance of continued employment, workers have now raised their expectations in other areas. For instance, employees expect employers to demonstrate their commitment in terms of pleasant working conditions, access to training and development, provision of a safe working environment and a balance between work and employees' commitments outside the workplace (Grahn, 2000).

Organizations are faced with ever-increasing competition and as they prepare for new challenges, one of the key components of survival is maintaining and upgrading the organization's ability to use human resources effectively and efficiently. According to Katz (1964), employee behavior essential for organizational effectiveness includes employees entering and remaining with the organization, carrying out specific role

requirements, and engaging in innovative and spontaneous activity that goes beyond role prescriptions. This appointment of good workers is thus critical, but of even greater significance is the organization's ability to create a committed workforce. Hence the need for managers to understand the concept of commitment - what it is, how it operates, and most importantly, which behaviors are displayed by employees committed to the organization.

The importance of employee commitment is quite evident if one considers prior research into the relationship between commitment and job satisfaction (Bateman & Organ, 1983), workplace justice (Moorman, Niehoff & Organ, 1992), trust in and loyalty to the leader (Deluga, 1994) and perceptions of supervisor fairness (Niehoff & Moorman, 1993).

One of the aims of this study is to determine how employees' perception fairness influence their commitment and the meaning of the concept will, therefore, be explained with reference to Meyer and Allen's (1997) developed the three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. They pick out the importance of employee commitment; the factors affecting it and how organizations should build employee commitment will also be discussed. That concept known as organizational citizenship behaviors is closely related to commitment.

Organizational commitment has been labeled as a key determinant and the driving force of many positive organizational level outcomes (Khan, I. (2013). Organizational commitment is referred to as the Psychological link between the employee and organization which makes the employee leaving the organization voluntarily less likely (Allen & Meyer, 1996). They said that People working for organizations "have certain needs, desires, skills, and so forth and expect to find a work environment where they can utilize their abilities and satisfy many of their basic needs" (Dessler, 2005). Organizational commitment can be increased if an organization is successful in providing such a vehicle.

Employee commitment has been linked to several positive results namely lower turnover rate and absenteeism, a higher level of motivation and job satisfaction, lower operating costs, higher productivity and higher efficiency (Morrow, 1993; Meyer & Allen, 1996; Lieu, 2008). Thus a committed employee can be favorable to the organization and its goals.

Statement of the problem

No organization in today's competitive world can perform at peak levels unless each employee is committed to the organization's objectives and works as an effective team member. It is no longer good enough to have employees who come to work faithfully every day and do their jobs independently (Dr. Varsha Dixit 2012). Employees now have to think like entrepreneurs while working in teams, and have to prove their worth. However, they also want to be part of a successful organization which provides a good income and the opportunity for development and secure employment. In the past, organizations secured the loyalty of their employees by guaranteeing job security. However, many organizations have responded to competitive pressures by downsizing, restructuring, and transformation and thus created a less secure organizational climate. A growing number of employees, therefore, feel that they are victims of broken promises. One of the challenges facing modern organizations involves maintaining employee commitment in the current business environment Buchanan, B. (1974). This organization can achieve by developing a new "work contract". In today's workplace, employees face more ambiguity in their daily activities and decreased job security (Bergmann, Lester, De Meuse & Grahn, 2000).

Over the last years, the study of commitment has advanced in many different directions. A variety of disciplines have adopted the topic as a theme in their research and these have offered fresh and significant insights. These recent advances include new approaches to both the conceptualization of employee commitment and the particular human resource practices intended to increase it (Osemeke 2016).

The workplace is changing dramatically and demands for the highest quality of product and service are increasing. To remain competitive in the face of these pressures, employee commitment is crucial. Without employee commitment, there can be no improvement in any area of business activity. Besides this; employees

treat their work without any burning desire to accomplish any more than is necessary to remain employed (Maicibi, 2003).

The Research Question

- How the rewards have an influence on Employee Commitment at Academic staff in Wolaita Sodo University?
- Does career development have an influence on the Employee Commitment?
- Do training and development opportunities have an influence on the Employee Commitment?
- Do the management styles have an influence on Staff Commitment?

Specific Objectives

- To pick-out factors that determine Employees' Commitment to Academic staff in Wolaita Sodo University.
- To list the influences of career development on the Employee Commitment of Wolaita Sodo University
- To determine the influence of training and development opportunities on the Employee Commitment of Wolaita Sodo University
- To find out the scope of management styles that affects Employee Commitment at Wolaita Sodo University

Research Methodology

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework deals with variables which are dependent that is Employee Commitments and variables which are independent, that is Rewards, Career development, training and development, and Management style.

Fig 1: Independent Variables & Dependent Variable

Research Design

The study adopted a causal Research design. Causal research, as the name specifies, tried to determine the cause underlying a given behavior. It finds the cause and determinants relationship between variables. It seeks to determine how the dependent variable changes with variations in the independent variable. Causal research is conducted in order to identify the extent and nature of cause-and-determinants relationships. Causal research

can be conducted in order to assess the impacts of specific changes on existing norms, various processes. Causal Research explores the determinants of one thing on another and more specifically, the determinants of one variable on another.

Sampling Design

The researchers used a stratified sampling technique by classifying the population into strata. The sample comprised of 10% from each strata of the target population. According to Mugenda, (1999) a sample of 10% is considered as a representative. Respondents were selected randomly based on the category. This approach is considered appropriate since ensured a representative sample. In order to find the best possible sample, stratified sampling was the best method to use as provided reach and in-depth information. The sample size is appropriate for the study as it ensured that all the respondents in the organization are represented thus reducing sampling bias and achieving a high level of representation.

Data source and type

In the process of carrying out the study, both primary and secondary data sources were used. Primary data conducted through questionnaire and interview while secondary data gathered from books, internet, published and unpublished documents.

Data collection tools

The researchers were used with different data collection tools. From different tools closed questionnaires and interviews are the major one. The data collected through questionnaires, interviews and field observation will be analyzed. The Likert 4 Point rating scale of 4, 3, 2, and 1 were used to analyze responses.

The researchers have conducted a Multiple Regression Analysis so as to assess the determinants of Staff commitments of Wolaita Sodo University. The researchers applied the statistical package SPSS version 20, to enter and compute the measurements of the multiple regressions for the study.

Data Analysis and Presentation

Before processing the responses, the completed questionnaires were edited for completeness and consistency. The data then coded to enable the responses to be grouped into various categories. Data collected analyzed by descriptive statistics. In addition, to determine the level of significance between the independent variables and the dependent variable, regression analysis was employed.

Instrumentation

The survey instrument used for the study consisted of 55 items measuring the five variables included in this study.

All the questions were measured using a 4-Point Likert type (with responses ranging from Strongly Agree= SA; Agree = A; Disagree = D; and Strongly Disagree = SD) scale and were tested for reliability and validity. The reliability of the study was verified by the Cronbach's alpha. The Cronbach's alpha is a technique that helps to determine the reliability of a survey instrument and the internal consistency of the average correlation of variables in the survey (Gleim and Gleim, 2003).

The accepted value for the cognitive test Alpha is equal to or greater than 0.7 ($\alpha=0.7$). Table 1 presents a summary of the reliability results of the instruments based on the pilot test carried out prior to the actual data collection.

Variables	No. of Items	Cronback alpha (α)
Employees' commitment (EC)	11	0.82
Reward @	11	0.73
Career Development (CD)	11	0.81
Training and development (TD)	11	0.73
Management Style (MS)	11	0.75

Source: Data Collected December 2018

Results and Discussions

Table 2 Demographic Findings of Research Participants (n=136)

Group	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Female	29	21.3
	Male	107	78.7
Age	UNDER 25-29	1	0.7
	30 - 35 years	16	11.8
	36-40 years	95	69.9
	41-45 years	14	10.3
	46+ years	10	7.4
Education	DEGREE	22	16.2
	MA & ABOVE	114	83.8
Service	10+ years	75	55.1
	5-10 years	6	4.4
	Less 5 years	55	40.4
Position	LOWER	47	34.6
	MIDDLE	89	65.4

Source: Researchers' Data Base

The researchers understood from Table 1 that 29(21.3 percent) of the participants were female while 107(78.7 percent) were male. This shows there is gender bias in the Wolaita Sodo University demographic profiles. On account of the nature of operation of the University, it employees more males than females mostly because the nature of the mandate (human resource management) requires more service of those with human resources knowledge which tended to be dominated by males, hence the gender bias in the sample. Such bias is likely to influence responses. When the respondents' age was evaluated, it is found that only one of them (0.7 percent) were under 29 years old, 16 of them (11.8 percent) are in the age bracket of 30-35 years, 95 of them (69.9 percent) are in the age bracket of 36-40 years, 14 of them (10.3 percent) were between 41-45 years of age and 10 of them (7.4 percent) were above 46 years old. These imply that most of the participants were matured and above mid-aged people who knew what was being asked of them. When the respondents' educational qualification is evaluated, it is found that 114(83.8 percent) have received post graduate qualifications, 22(16.2 per cent), and are bachelor degree's holders. This indicates the respondents were almost fairly knowledge on the study variables. When the respondents' tenure in the University is evaluated, results indicated that 75(55.1 per cent) have worked for above 10 years, 6(4.4 per cent) have worked for between 5to 10 years, and the greater number 55(40.4 percent) have already worked for less than 5 years. In a comparison of these data's, academic staffs that have more experience, positioned, matured and middle positioned staff 89 (65.4). This implies that, if the University works more on their need, there is more probability to get more committed academic staffs.

Statistical Model Findings Analysis for Hypothesis

To achieve the purpose of this study, Pearson's correlation was carried out to verify if there existed a relationship between the independent variables (Rewards(R)(X1), Career development(CD)(X2), training and development(TD)(X3) and Management style(MS)(X4), and the dependent variable(determinants of employee's commitment(EC)(Y)). This analysis served to test four hypotheses. In addition to these hypotheses, the researchers were employed multiple regression analysis to determine the predictive value of the model in explaining employee's commitment.

Hypothesis 1-4: There is a relationship between Reward, Career Development, Training and Development and Management Styles with an academic staff Employee’s Commitment.

The results suggest that, Reward is positively correlated to employee commitment ($r = .855$, $\text{Sig.} = 0.000$). Therefore, the researchers conclude that, the hypothesis was accepted and that there is a strong positive relationship between reward and employee’s commitment (see Table 3).

The Wolaita Sodo University employee commitment has almost strong correlations with carrier development, and training and development and management styles ($r = 0.404$ sig. = 0.000, $r = 0.903$ sig. 0.000 and $r=476$ sig. =0.000 respectively).

		Y ((EC))	x1 ((R))	x2 ((CD))	x3 ((TD))	x4 ((MS))
Pearson Correlation	Y ((EC))	1.000	.855	.404	.903	.476
	x1((R))	.855	1.000	.398	.872	.692
	x2((CD))	.404	.398	1.000	.472	-.182
	x3 ((TD))	.903	.872	.472	1.000	.532
	x4 ((MS))	.476	.692	-.182	.532	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Y ((EC))	.	.000	.000	.000	.000
	x1((R))	.000	.	.000	.000	.000
	x2((CD))	.000	.000	.	.000	.020
	x3 ((TD))	.000	.000	.000	.	.000
	x4 ((MS))	.000	.000	.020	.000	.
N	Y ((EC))	136	136	136	136	136
	x1((R))	136	136	136	136	136
	x2((CD))	136	136	136	136	136
	x3 ((TD))	136	136	136	136	136
	x4 ((MS))	136	136	136	136	136

To understand commitment in the given sample of ANOVA calculation and multiple regression model analysis was carried out to test the hypothesized model. The model comprised of the four independent variables (Reward, career development, training and development, and University management styles) and the dependent variable (employee commitment). The results of these analyses are presented in Table 4, 5 and 6. The model suggests that Reward, career development, training and development, and University management styles predicts employee commitment (sig. = 0.000). Further, evaluating the strength of each independent variable revealed in the β coefficients training and development (TD) appeared to be the best predictor of employee commitment with a β coefficient of 0.662 (See Table 5).

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df 1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.926 ^a	.858	.853	.18314	.858	185.776	4	123	.000

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	24.924	4	6.231	185.776	.000 ^p
	Residual	4.126	123	.034		
	Total	29.050	127			

a. Dependent Variable: y (EC)= employee commitment
 b. Predictors: (Constant), x4 MS, x2 CD, x3 TD, x1 R

Source: Data collection 2018

Table 6. Coefficients of Employee predictors

Model	Un-standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations		
	B	Std. Error				Beta	Zero-order	Partial
(EC)Const	1.746	.236		7.410	.000			
x1 R	.458	.076	.553	6.043	.000	.855	.478	.205
x2 CR	-.217	.062	.482	-3.489	.001	.404	-.300	-.119
x3 TD	.568	.062	.662	9.161	.000	.903	.637	.311
x4 MS	-.307	.068	-.293	-4.504	.000	.476	-.376	-.153

a. Dependent Variable: y Employee Commitment

The predictive model developed in this study had an R Square value of 0. 858 with Adjusted R Square value of 0. 853. This means that (Reward, Career Development, Training and Development, and Management Styles) together explain 85% variance in employee commitment. Of the selected variables in the study Training and Development emerged as the best predictor of employee commitment. Since the given model explains 85% variance in employee commitment, there are other variables that account for only 15% of the variance in the construct.

The equation for the employee commitment model as a result of this study is:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4$$

$$y = 1.746 + .553(\beta R) + (.482) (\beta CR) + 0.662(\beta TD) + (-.293) (\beta TD)$$

Where:

- Y = Employees' Commitment (Predicted Variable)
- β_0 = Constant value or Y intercept
- βR = Reward (Predictor Variable)
- βCR = Career Development (Predictor Variable)
- βTD = Training and Development (Predictor Variable)
- βMS = Management Styles (Predictor Variable)

The model developed in this study is significant and explains employees' commitment in Wolaita Sodo University academic staff. Although reward, Career development, training and development, and management styles are predictors in this model; the university management styles are weak and account for little variance in the construct. Additionally, training and development were evidenced as the strongest predictor in the model.

The findings of this study provide support for existing literature relating to commitment (Al- Gilsson 1988; Savery 1994; Wilson 1995).

The researchers suggest that when employees get training and development with their job, they are more likely to understanding higher levels of commitment to their organizations. Besides this, when employees perceive opportunities of training and development (short or long term) in their employing organizations of Wolaita Sodo University and are employed in favorable working culture, they tend to be more committed.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The study wanted to build up a predictive model that explains commitment among academic staff of Wolaita Sodo University. The findings provide empirical support for existing studies and as such contribute to commitment literature as general. It enhances employee's commitment and consequently their productivity in the education sector. The findings of the study, at large, suggests that in order to enhance employees' commitment in the sector, management efforts must be directed to improve the training and development mechanisms to academic staff. Additionally, commitment may be enhanced by arranging different award and improving their management styles to get committed staff in every time.

Since training and development variable emerged as the best predictor of employees' commitment in this sample the researchers suggest that future research endeavors investigate factors that enhance this in similar contexts. Additionally, since there were strong correlations among the independent variables, future studies may work on modeling techniques to understand the influence each variable has on each other.

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